

**HUSEYN BOYKARO'S SKILLS IN PUBLIC ADMINISTRATION AND
POLITICS, BUT ALSO IN THE MANAGEMENT OF LITERARY
PROCESSES IN KHAZOYIN UL-MAONI**

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Annotation: His thoughts on governance show that he was not only a great poet, but also a brilliant statesman, a man of high potential and enthusiasm, a wise leader with great influence.

Keywords: motivation of employees, centralization of activities, justice, motive, example, decision-making, political processes.

Introduction

The life and work of Alisher Navoi falls on a period of events that took place not only in Movarounnahr and Khorasan, but also in the whole world, which happened a lot and went sharply. As early as his childhood, there were alma-shinys of power that caused bloody clashes in Khorasan and Movarounnahr. At a young age, radical changes took place in Khorasan, in particular Herat management ti-Zim. He was unable to stay away from a series of uprisings in the country, stability-derailing disputes, disagreements between political groups and representatives of the system of government, both in his Middle Ages and in his aging chog'es. Nevertheless, he created many works, effectively creating ni-hoyat. In addition to the volume of his works, each of them, in its rarity, has become an indelible and huge contribution to the treasury of world literature. These works cover the diverse themes and motives of artistic creativity, and of course, the issues of politics, management and the sphere of leadership are also included in them. Some of his poems, focused on these issues, are directly related to the events of his life, while some are based on the conclusions he

draws from what he observed, heard and read. In this aspect, we found it necessary to focus on some of Alisher Navoi's works below.

The main of results

«**Хазойин ул-маоний**». The work of Alisher Navoi "Khazoyin ul-maoni" is composed of poems of the lyrical genre, which in this direction covers mainly works created throughout his life. The work is also popularly mentioned under the names "head devon", "Culliyot" and is indeed composed of four independent devons. In his first office called "Strange US-Qajar" ("childhood oddities"), Navoi composed this collection on the advice and assignment of the ruler Hussein Boyqaro [1:11]. Even before that, Badoyi'ul-Bidaya and Navodur un-nihaya formed two devons and handed them over to aizzayi ashob and ajillayi ahbob services, which is in the order of two devon ... both of these are poor...the GHA has no power, because all know the sultanic judgments, and the admonitions, and the Noble Commandments, and the interpretations..."reports that it was [1:6]. These words of Navoi (although historians have ended many times in their works) indicate that Judge-dor Hussein Boykaro, among other areas, was a salo-talented person in artistic creativity, a curious leader with various creative and creative works. In some of Navoi's definitions, Husayn placed Boykaro in the heart of God a treasure of knowledge and a multifaceted connoisseur of various fields, and he himself is as humble as the soil, and although God confesses his interests and aspirations and makes him one of the big (rulers)of the world, he evaluates himself as a lower-seerment of all, a We can give an example of this the following ruboies of Navoi:

The truth lies in the knowledge of the truth, the letter of the Lord, and the throne of the Lord(i.e. Charkhi musamman).

Huseyn Boykaro's letter (order), which cited Navoi's content, proves that he was a deeply educated ruler of the idea not only about public administration and politics, but also about the management of literary processes, artistic creation. In it, Hussein wrote to Boykaro Navoi that" two devonkim noses, our judgment and our cry bila

murattab, and culliyotu gizviyotin with correcting " 1:9-11]. Also in the letter Huseyn Boyqaro wrote his poem to Navoi-as rini gathered and burdened with the task of forming four devons, this work was done by few people in history, Amir Khusraviy Sultan Malikshah Alp Lion sha-Rafi is also reminded of the fact that he composed such four Devons from his poems, but whether they are now (that time) is unknown [1:11]. From this, tash-old Navoi writes that during the creation of "Khazoyin"he collected his poems and sent them to the ruler, and he edited them in different aspects, corrected their mistakes and shortcomings, determined the place of each poem in Devon, sent messages on existing shortcomings and corrected places [1:15]. The poet noted that Hussein Boykaro was a direct follower of Navoi in the formation of this Devonian: "shokhvashlar (poems-F.R. fifty, sixty, or about a hundred... I put the Sultan in the Palace of the harem of Sahibkiran and gave one by one to The Alchemist of His Majesty... and his Lord looked at alargha compassion face, which means scorn (poem-F.R.) if he sees without welcome in the composition of iningkim Khil'ati and alfozi kiswati, then his ganjinayi zamiri khizonasidin gives a worthy alfoz bila ul li-boslargga tagyir and in ul alfoz kiswati industrial'javohiridin nomuno-sibligma, his khizanayi wife ganjkhanasidin... and every Gazelle will be given a number in its place in order, " [1: 15-16]. All of these recognize that Hussein Boykaro is well versed in artistic creation, the history of literature, is in great respect for the creators, appreciates them and, if necessary, personally appreciates their position in society. Navoi even noted his deep knowledge and high potential, and writes that the name of Devon is based on these qualities, since it is a treasure of knowledge: "the meaning of all ul Hazrat tab'i bahridinu mental conidin was formed, and the khazoyini hamul meanings consisting of alfozu gavharidin was filled, this meaning aning atin "Khazoyin ul-maoni" was put" [1:16]. Navoi also emphasizes this recognition with the following ruboiyi:

This is bahrki, ganji lomakani said,
They said, " every one of them is in prison.",
They called the tab'id mark of Shah mahzani

And they said, "Be Thou The King."

From the point of view of creativity Alisher Navoi called the ruler "word Beth ul-harami... and nazm shahbayti " speaks with definitions [1:6]. Historical sources also confirm that there were many events related to creative, literary, ij-thymoi-economic, culture, enlightenment in the Huseyn Boykaro House, palace, many talented and ordinary people had the opportunity to work and express their opinions at these meetings. And these aspects make the definitions that Navoi gave to the ruler and his mansion much more realistic. The poet also commented that it is painful that he was among 50 to 60 young people in bithat-Gan, having created "Khazoyin ul-Mauni", and for most of his life he was busy with state affairs and could not create freely.

«**Ғаройиб ус-сигар**». Navoi, as we noted above, lived in an era of drastic changes. This period, in which he himself was a participant, he brilliantly describes in an idea with a word game. In the essence of this image, due to the changes taking place within the state and society, there was no attention of the opinions of people before the authorities, or due to robberies, the state of society of political, military and other circles (including positional ones) was envisaged-F.R. the idea of a society that has nothing to do with it or that the management system is unbridled. It is also similar to the fact that people are not independent in doing something, either their needs are too high, or the extreme rigor or instability of power, no matter who is in such a time, if God has a talent for his forehead (ability-F.R.) if he has not given, it is noted that he has no land neither in himself nor in what he does:

No attention to the man in the say,
Nor do you have the right to a person,
Fate aro becuase no Gifted Man,
What do you do [1:7].

Summarizing the description of the events that took place at the time of youth, when Navoi began to write poems, brings this ruboi with connection. Because, in old

age (in the vaq-tida – F, which is forming "Khazoyin"),R.) when he remembered his youth ,he said, " again, fasting whether (from past days eventsF.R.) ul thoughts (memories-F.R.) all the disappointment went (I remember – F.R.), (reason – F.R.(the world) allingah sa'b (hard) turned into giriftorlarigah and sipehr (the world) onгах onгах balo stone ottiyu ishq sipohi's lagadkobi (Te-pib ezeki) weak paykarim (tanim) know that after I hold my things under my feet onгахattikim, ne sökümdin hissimu ne ozlugimdin my work remained", writes [1:7]. In fact, Navoi's youth was a time of great change. When Abulkosim Babur died, he annexed Khorasan to Mirzo Abusaid Movarounnahr and tried to restore Turun. This is assessed as a negative phenomenon from the point of view of the contradictions, complexities arising in management processes, even if it is a positive phenomenon from the point of view of the general political situation of Turan. At this time, the Khurasan system of government was obliged to beysu-Nish to the representatives of the Movarounnahr authorities who came with Abusaid. Navoi later wrote about this: "in the time of Sultan Abusaid Mirzo, the people of Khurasan captivated the people of Samarkand, and every cruel and taaddiki, alardin Haydar become, these captives are mute, and farmanpazir". Mirzo Abusaid is mentioned in another place by Alisher Navoi under the name "dear king". But his service system did not understand Abusaid's ideas and goals, as we think, enough. Because, when Khurasan is subdued, these servants will end the system of government created by Shahruh and Abulkosim Babur, and will especially rob the entire population of Herat, as Navoi wrote in Navadir ush-Shabob.

In managerial work, the desire to bring their ideas to life in a capable person becomes paramount. This situation was also in Navoi. As he remembers about it, he said that, no matter how high his passion for action was, he could not find a single sympathy to relieve himself by saying a twinge of his pain, as a result of which he poured all his existing mu-lohazas into his poems, and over time a bunch of his poems accumulated in his hands, which mainly (Navoi later collected them and put them in the "strange us-Fitar") [1:502-525]. When Navoi thought to collect them and devon

them, they said, "chun ul Ta'rikhdin du termte ottiyu ul vøtdin oluntare arağa" [1:8], the processes changed and (it is envisaged that Husayn Boykaro would seize power here-F.R.) he becomes an active representative of the political power and Management System [1:8]. So, according to Navoi's own notes, the "strange us-capacar" office included poems from the period "tufuliyyat avonikim, seven-sekiz yoshdin twenty years old-until chinasa olgaykim, the turn of the life fusuli and the life Gulshan shukufavu gulzidur" [1:17], which also serves to reveal the poet's condition of that period, the processes taking place in the country, the life of society, the various facets of the management system.

Navoi writes that during the Abusaid period he experienced many difficulties, without even finding a single interlocutor. But even during these periods, he does not strike his pride on the ground. In circles, he argues that not speaking too much should be said with knowledge if it is spoken, and says that it is necessary for a person to maintain his seriousness wherever he is. Dar-truth, he himself did not see himself beating his head in front of the representatives of the management system, whom he considered a yacht in those difficult times. "Viqor" did not give way to this, as he noted. And in his contemporaries, although the poet was a very gentle, kind, "calm" person, there were also those who, with this Dignity, led him into arrogance. But Navoi always honored this pride as a personality trait. He describes the seriousness in the most correct way si-fat, which attracts and subjugates everyone in human prestige, mutual respect. That is, a person must have the dignity that he values, and at the same time kindness, which he describes as a leadership trait that brings gadoyu-King to obedience if necessary:

The Holy Quran,

If you say, go to obedience you poor with King.

This dialect appeared on the mountain, you behaved

When the divide was seven, public became refuge [1: 531].

But Khandamir wrote that when Navoi became El, he forgot about this VI-snow: "when he saw from Sahibqiron (Hussein Boyqaro), the owner of great power, that Grace and kindness towards him were increasing day by day, he went to a deserted place, nodded, scattered some soil from the top of his blessed head, and said to his elegant body:" the higher careers and ranks in this Never give in to meanness and arrogance that you have reached these careers and careers. Knowing yourself a soil on the road, try to meet and help the needs of the poor and the needy as much as possible" [3:104-105]. Indeed, the life and character of Navoi is very consistent with the content of this continent.

Navoi emphasizes correctness as one of the most important requirements for working in the management system. The correctness he interprets can be understood in different meanings, at the same time in the colorful manifestations of justice and goodness. That is, the correctness of a person cannot be different from one aspect, and from another. Navoi noted that if a manager wants stability in his work, he must first make this right his law.

Navoi noted that another feature of human stability in management activities is caution in language. During the Navoi period, being in the service of the kingdom, dealing with people, communicating with the ruler, correctly interpreting judgments and decrees, expressing feedback on them, giving inappropriate, impudent, besabial and insensitive opinions about the affairs inherent in managerial activity in general were the periods that caused people to separate not only career, prestige, family, property, but even head-on. Although power is the goal of establishing a head-care system, in which those who operate are considered to be the joint supports of this state, in the internal state there were many groups of political, economic, legal and other goals and interests. This situation was observed in all public administration systems of that time, before and after. The management systems of current states are no exception. Only in modern political systems is the rule "let the opposition stand before you and work with you." This phenomenon can also be seen in history, but in those days it was

subordinated to this disorganized power and acquired a hidden appearance. Any manifestation of going against the ruler's policy, although this resistance was not aimed at taking power, led to cruel punishment. Navoi had called on the management staff to be wary of such innocence as:

Look, the mouth of the arrow is for the tongue-free,
Do the merchants know dastbus.
How many crowns cutars head,
Chu hangomless Nagma tortar hurus [1:534].

Navoi also warns service personnel from situations that arise from being close to the leader. That is, in the management system, a tradition that has been going on from very ancient times to the present day is become, according to which in the Tegra of the leader who has taken a managerial position, persons who are definitely related or spiritually close to him will gather. Or rather, when a leading person comes to a career position, appoints certain persons to positions close to him or introduces special privileges for them in specific forms, according to a number of goals, such as completing tasks, obtaining advice on make, thinking, ensuring the quality of work that needs to be done. This is justified by the formation of a management team in modern management theories. A person close to the leader of the team can become a partner in all his assignments, tasks, duties, powers, initiatives, goals and interests, even in his ideas and thinking. Such cases are not uncommon even in modern times.

Conclusion

To conclude, The ideas characteristic of Navoi for his views on the issues of the state, society, culture of Management, Man-care occupy a wide place in his lyric poetry.

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